

KARYA TULIS ILMIAH

PENGEMBANGAN BIO-WRAPPING PLASTIC BERBASIS POLIMER ALAMI DAN EKSTRAK KULIT BAWANG MERAH DENGAN TAMBAHAN IRADIASI GAMMA

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DEVELOPMENT OF BIO-WRAPPING PLASTIC FROM GELATIN MATRIX ENHANCED WITH NATURAL PIGMENTS FROM RED ONION PEEL AND GAMMA IRRADIATION TREATMENT

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ABSTRACT

DEVELOPMENT OF BIO-WRAPPING PLASTIC FROM GELATIN MATRIX ENHANCED WITH NATURAL PIGMENTS FROM RED ONION PEEL AND GAMMA IRRADIATION TREATMENT. Utilizing waste to produce value-added products is a strategy that supports environmental sustainability by reducing the burden on landfills and offering more economical and efficient solutions. One such potential waste is red onion peel, which contains anthocyanin compounds—natural pigments sensitive to pH changes. This characteristic allows anthocyanins to serve as indicators of food quality, as their color changes in response to pH fluctuations. During food spoilage, microorganisms generate various decomposition gases with acidic or basic properties, which can trigger changes in anthocyanin color. Based on this potential, this study aims to develop a bio-wrapping plastic made from natural polymers integrated with red onion peel extract as a spoilage indicator. The product is formulated using three main components: natural polymer as the matrix, red onion peel extract as the color indicator, and glycerol as a plasticizer. To improve the mechanical properties of the bioplastic to be comparable with conventional plastic, gamma irradiation treatment using Cobalt-60 at doses of 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 kGy was applied. This research aims to produce an environmentally friendly food wrap that not only serves as food protection but also provides visual information about the freshness of the packaged product. This innovation has the potential to support the development of smart packaging in Indonesia and promote the utilization of organic waste into high-value functional products.

Keywords: bio-wrapping plastic, red onion extract, smart packaging, gamma irradiation.

INTRODUCTION

The issue of environmental pollution caused by plastic waste has long been a global environmental concern, and its severity increases each year due to the continuously growing quantity of plastic waste. According to Earth.Org, plastic waste is among the 15 biggest environmental problems currently faced worldwide.[1]. In Indonesia, the food sector is one of the largest contributors to plastic usage, particularly for packaging. Conventional food packaging plastics are typically made from materials such as polyethylene (PE), polypropylene (PP), and polyethylene terephthalate (PET), which have stable chemical structures and are therefore difficult to fully decompose resulting in the accumulation of plastic waste.[2]. The accumulation of plastic waste can have severe consequences for the environment, particularly the soil, as it obstructs various components, including the flow of water and air within the soil.

Moreover, these plastics can fragment into microplastics that may spread widely in the environment, especially within marine ecosystems. These microplastics can be ingested by fish and other aquatic organisms, eventually entering the food chain. When humans consume fish contaminated with microplastics, the particles can accumulate in the body, causing inflammation, oxidative stress, and metabolic disorders. Research has shown that exposure to microplastics can also disrupt the immune system and potentially trigger long-term illnesses, making microplastics a serious threat to both human health and the environment as a whole. [3].

As a solution to this problem, extensive research and development on bioplastics is currently being conducted. Unlike conventional plastics, bioplastics are made from natural polymers such as starch, gelatin, or cellulose, which can biodegrade relatively quickly through microbial activity. This characteristic makes bioplastics more environmentally friendly, as they do not leave long-lasting residues. However, bioplastics generally have weaknesses in terms of mechanical strength and durability compared to petrochemical-based plastics. To address this challenge, this study develops a gelatin-based bioplastic treated with Cobalt-60 (Co-60) irradiation to promote crosslinking between polymer chains, resulting in a bioplastic with improved strength and stability.

In addition to focusing on reducing plastic waste, this study also introduces an innovation by incorporating red onion peel extract as both a natural colorant for the bioplastic and a spoilage indicator for food. The inclusion of this material is motivated by the limited use of red onion peels, which have not yet been widely adopted by the public. On the other hand, several studies conducted by Virliantari et al., Kasnati et al., and Yusuf et al. have shown that red onion peel extract has high sensitivity to pH range changes, making it a promising candidate for use as an acid-base indicator [4] [5] [6]. Red onion peel extract is known to undergo significant color changes in response to environmental pH variations. This is due to its anthocyanin content, a natural pigment belonging to the flavonoid group that is highly sensitive to acidity and alkalinity levels. Research by Virliantari et al. showed that red onion peel extract changes to a reddish color under acidic conditions (low pH) and turns greenish under alkaline conditions (high pH).

This color-changing characteristic offers significant potential for the development of smart packaging based on pH indicators. Food spoilage is known to cause changes in environmental pH, as microorganisms produce volatile compounds such as ammonia, dimethylamine, and trimethylamine, which are alkaline, as well as organic acids like butyric acid and lactic acid, depending on the type of substrate and microbes involved. The accumulation of these compounds within the packaging environment causes the air around the food to become more acidic or basic, depending on the stage and type of spoilage. By utilizing red onion peel extract as a pH indicator in the packaging, the resulting color changes due to pH shifts can serve as a visual cue to indicate the freshness or spoilage level of the product. This aligns with the findings of Noor Azizah Ahmad et al. (2018), which demonstrated that anthocyanin pigments in bilberry extract exhibit a linear and quantifiable color response to pH changes, making them highly promising for use as pH sensors in food freshness monitoring systems. [7].

By integrating red onion peel extract into the bioplastic, a smart packaging system has been developed that is not only environmentally friendly and biodegradable but also capable of providing visual information about the condition of the packaged food. This innovation is expected to serve as a functional solution for reducing plastic waste while simultaneously enhancing the value of organic waste.

As a developing country, Indonesia still faces many challenges related to environmental issues, one of which is plastic waste. According to data from the National Waste Management Information System (SIPSN), Indonesia generated approximately 33.8 million tons of waste in 2024, with 19.75% of it consisting of plastic waste. [8]. Non-biodegradable plastic waste poses a major threat to the environment, endangering both marine and terrestrial ecosystems. The increasing amount of plastic waste each year highlights the urgent need to develop environmentally friendly alternative solutions. Currently, many studies focus on the development of bioplastics as substitutes for petroleum-based plastics, which are made from natural polymers such as starch and gelatin. These natural polymers are more easily degraded due to their simpler chemical structures, making them more susceptible to both chemical and enzymatic hydrolysis. This hydrolysis process allows microorganisms, such as bacteria and fungi, to break down the polymers into metabolizable monomers, thereby accelerating degradation and reducing environmental impact. [9].

Natural plastics, commonly referred to as bioplastics, are a type of plastic derived from renewable biological sources and are biodegradable through microbial activity. Scientifically, bioplastics can be defined as polymers synthesized from natural sources such as polysaccharides (starch and cellulose), proteins (gelatin and casein), or lipids, offering a more environmentally friendly alternative to conventional petrochemical-based plastics. [10], [11]. One of the most commonly used raw materials in the production of bioplastics is gelatin.

Gelatin is a natural biopolymer obtained through the hydrolysis of collagen from animal connective tissues such as skin, bones, and tendons. Chemically, gelatin consists of polypeptide chains with varying molecular weights and contains reactive functional groups such as amino, carboxyl, and hydroxyl groups. [12] [13]. The main characteristics of gelatin include its solubility in warm water, its ability to form elastic gels, and its capacity to create transparent and flexible films. Domestic research has also shown that gelatin extracted from catfish bones and local cattle possesses good viscosity and film-forming ability, making it suitable for bioplastic production. [14] [15]. These properties make gelatin a promising raw material for bioplastics, as it is not only easy to modify but can also be processed under relatively mild environmental conditions, supporting the principles of sustainability.

Figure 1. Illustrations of the effect of cross-linking on gelatin network structure [16].

One method that can be used to improve the mechanical properties of bioplastics is by inducing crosslinking within the polymer. Crosslinking is the process of forming chemical bonds between polymer molecules, linking one polymer chain to another. This process results in a three-dimensional network structure, which increases the molecular weight and density of the material. One way to induce crosslinking is through the use of cobalt-60 irradiation.[17].

Cobalt-60 irradiation produces high-energy gamma rays capable of breaking chemical bonds within polymer chains, forming free radicals within the polymer structure. These free radicals then react with one another to form covalent bonds between chains, resulting in crosslinking that transforms the polymer structure from linear into a three-dimensional network, as previously described.

In addition to bioplastic development, this study introduces an innovation by adding natural pigments to the bioplastic using red onion peel waste. Although classified as waste, red onion peels have been proven to still contain anthocyanins that can be utilized as natural pigments. [18]. Anthocyanins are compounds classified within the flavonoid group, with a basic structure consisting of two aromatic benzene rings (C_6H_6) connected by three carbon atoms that form an additional ring. [19].

Figure 2. Chemical Structure of Anthocyanin [19]

The main characteristic of anthocyanins is their ability to change color depending on the acidity (pH) of their environment. In acidic conditions (low pH), anthocyanins tend to appear red; at neutral pH, they turn purple; and in alkaline conditions (high pH), their color can shift to blue or even greenish. This color change occurs due to the transformation of the anthocyanin's chemical structure, which is highly sensitive to pH. [20].

About the product developed in this study, which is intended for smart packaging capable of detecting spoilage, it is known that food spoilage can alter the pH of the air surrounding the food. During the spoilage process, various volatile compounds are produced by microorganisms such as bacteria and fungi. These compounds include ammonia (NH_3), sulfur compounds (such as hydrogen sulfide), and organic acids (such as butyric acid, propionic acid, and acetic acid). Ammonia is basic and can raise the environmental pH, while organic acids are acidic and

lower the pH. Therefore, when food begins to spoil, the anthocyanins embedded in the bio-wrapping plastic are expected to change color, with this change serving as an indicator of the spoilage level of the packaged food.

METHOD/EXPERIMENT

This research began with material preparation, anthocyanin extraction from red onion peels, bio-wrapping plastic production, and characterization testing.

Anthocyanin Extraction from Red Onion Peels

Red onion peel waste was obtained from household waste. The red onion peels used were still fresh, with a purplish-red color. The extraction was carried out using the maceration method, which involved boiling 10 gram of the chopped red onion peels in 50 mL distilled water (aquadest). The boiling temperature was maintained at 45°C to prevent degradation of the anthocyanin content. The boiling process lasted for approximately 60 minutes, accompanied by stirring with a magnetic stirrer to maximize the extraction of anthocyanins.

Bio-Wrapping Plastic Production

The bioplastic in this study was produced by modifying a method previously developed by Novianto et al. Five grams of fish gelatin were dissolved in 50 mL of aquadest, and the solution was heated to 60°C. The temperature was then lowered to 40°C, and 3 mL of glycerol was added. The mixture was homogenized again, and then 50 mL of red onion peel extract was added. The mixture was further homogenized for 30 minutes. Next, 30 mL of the mixture was poured into a 10 cm × 10 cm silicone mold. The bio-wrapping plastic was then air-dried at room temperature for 3 days.

Gamma Irradiation

The dried bio-wrapping plastic samples were exposed to gamma irradiation at absorbed doses of 2 kGy, 4 kGy, 6 kGy, and 8 kGy. The gamma irradiator employed in this study was a Type I irradiator utilizing a Cobalt-60 source, operated at the Center for Science, Technology, and Education, National Research and Innovation Agency (BRIN), Yogyakarta, Indonesia. The dose rate during the experiment was approximately 2050 Gy/hour.

Characterization Testing of the Bio-Wrapping Plastic

The following tests were conducted: soil degradation test, contact angle test, acid and base drop test, and food spoilage test.

RESULT

Soil Degradation Analysis

The soil degradation test for bioplastics aims to determine how quickly and to what extent the bioplastic decomposes naturally in a soil environment, simulating natural biodegradation conditions. This test is important because bioplastics are designed to replace conventional plastics, which are difficult to degrade. Based on the images in Table 1, after 24 hours of burial, the bio-wrapping plastic showed more visible signs of degradation compared to conventional plastic, which remained visually intact. Although the level of damage was not yet severe, the bio-wrapping plastic tended to exhibit surface degradation across all irradiation doses (from 0 kGy to 8 kGy). This indicates a higher potential for biological degradation compared to conventional food-wrapping plastic.

Contact Angle Test Analysis

The contact angle test results on the surface of the bio-wrapping plastic developed in this study show that all samples had contact angle values above 90°, as shown in Figure 1. Based on surface property classification, a contact angle above 90° indicates that the material surface is hydrophobic [21]. Therefore, it can be concluded that the gelatin-based bio-wrapping plastic with added red onion peel extract exhibits good water-repellent properties. Furthermore, increasing the irradiation dose tended to increase the contact angle, indicating enhanced hydrophobicity. Although there were minor fluctuations in some data points, the overall trend showed an increase in contact angle values with higher irradiation doses.

Hydrophobic bioplastics do not readily absorb water, making them more stable in humid environments, which is crucial for food packaging. Hydrophobic properties also slow the penetration of water which could trigger

early hydrolysis or biodegradation. The bioplastic remains strong during its intended use but can still degrade after its useful life. Absorbed water can weaken the polymer structure; therefore, bioplastics with higher hydrophobicity tend to be more tear-resistant and do not swell. This also indicates that the mechanical properties of the bioplastic improve along with its hydrophobicity.

Table 1. Bio-Wrapping Plastic Degradation Test Results

Variation	(0 hour)	24 Hours
0 kGy		
2 kGy		
4 kGy		
6 kGy		
8 kGy		

Figure 2. Contact angles of bio-wrapping plastic irradiated at doses of (a) 0 kGy – non-irradiated, (b) 2 kGy, (c) 4 kGy, (d) 6 kGy, (e) 8 kGy

Acid-Base Analysis

The acid-base drop test on red onion peel extract was conducted to evaluate its potential as a natural indicator for smart packaging. As previously explained, red onion peel extract contains anthocyanins. Under acidic conditions (low pH), anthocyanins tend to appear red; at neutral pH, they turn purple; and in alkaline conditions (high pH), the color can shift to blue or greenish. These color changes occur due to the transformation of the anthocyanin's chemical structure, which is highly sensitive to pH [20]. As shown in Figure 3, visual observation revealed significant color differences between the control sample (center), the sample treated with acid (left), and the sample treated with base (right). The acid-treated extract changed from orange to bright red, while the base-treated extract changed from orange to bluish-green. This test demonstrates the potential of red onion peel extract to be developed as a natural pigment for smart packaging applications.

Figure 3. Color change of red onion peel extract with the addition of acid (left), original extract (center), and with the addition of base (right).

Figure 4. Acid-base drop test on bio-wrapping plastic after being treated with base (left), acid (center), and control (right).

However, when the red onion peel extract was incorporated into the bioplastic matrix, the color changes observed during the drop test were not as distinct compared to those seen in the pure extract, as shown in Figure 3. The acid and base drop tests on the bio-wrapping plastic product were conducted to simulate real-life conditions where the packaging comes into contact with food undergoing spoilage. During spoilage, acidic or basic compounds are produced depending on the dominant nutrients present in the food. Protein-rich foods such as fish and meat tend to raise the pH (becoming more basic) as they spoil, while fruits, vegetables, or carbohydrate-based foods tend to lower the pH (becoming more acidic).

Based on visual observations (Figure 4), although the color changes were not very pronounced, the addition of acid (center sample) and base (left sample) still showed color differences compared to the control (right sample). This indicates that the developed bio-wrapping material is still responsive to chemical changes in its surrounding environment. The limited color response of the red onion peel pigment in the bio-wrapping plastic, compared to its pure extract form, may be due to the insufficient concentration of extract used in the bioplastic formulation. Additionally, an alternative method of incorporate the pigment during bioplastic production may be need to improve color responsiveness.

CONCLUSION

In this study, a bioplastic product in the form of wrapping plastic was developed, which demonstrated better degradability in natural environments compared to conventional wrapping plastics. The crosslinking process using gamma irradiation showed that increasing irradiation doses generally led to higher contact angles between the plastic surface and water, indicating improved hydrophobicity of the material. This supports the objective of promoting the application of nuclear technology in the packaging sector. The acid and base drop tests revealed that although the color changes were not yet significant, the observed visual responses indicated the initial potential of using red onion peel extract as an active indicator component in smart packaging concepts. With further optimization of formulation and processing methods, this potential can be further developed to more accurately detect food spoilage and enhance the value of red onion peel waste into a more useful product.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The development of this bio-wrapping plastic should focus on a more precise and stable formulation of material composition, including the optimization of irradiation doses to produce a product that meets the required specifications. Further research is needed on the extraction method of red onion peel to ensure the stability of anthocyanin active compounds and compatibility with food-grade standards, allowing broader application in the food packaging industry. Alternative methods are needed for incorporating pigment from red onion peel extract into the bioplastic base material.

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